

Resolution of Tris-biguanidinium Iridium(III) Complexes into Their Optical Isomers

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Tris-biguanidinium iridium(III) chloride has been resolved into its optical isomers by fractional crystallization of the diastereoisomer, tris-biguanidinium iridium (III) chloro-(+)-tartrate. Unlike diastereoisomer, tris-biguanidinium cobalt(III) chloro-(+)-tartrate, this iridium analogue, like the rhodium one, does not exhibit any "asymmetric transformation of the second order". The *laevo*-gyrate forms the less soluble variety and separates first. The (-)- and (+)-enantiomers of the complex chloro-(+)-tartrate, (-)- and (+)-complex chloride and nitrate have been obtained in a pure state and their optical rotations measured. The specific rotation of tris-biguanidinium iridium chloro-(+)-tartrate, $[\alpha]_D^{30} \pm 128^\circ$, is much less than the corresponding rhodium and cobalt complexes, viz., $[\alpha]_D^{30} \pm 140^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_D^{30} \pm 335^\circ$.

Biguanide, $C_2H_7N_5$, acts as a bidentate chelating agent, forming inner-metallic complex salts of the third order. With trivalent ions like Cr(III) and Co(III), it forms octahedral complexes¹. Rhodium(III)² and iridium(III)³ also form diamagnetic octahedral complexes with biguanide. The tris-biguanidinium complexes, like tris-ethylenediamine complexes, do not have any centre or plane of symmetry and therefore potentially resolvable into their optical isomers. The cobalt(III) complexes have been resolved by Rây and Dutta⁴. A very interesting phenomenon of "asymmetric transformation of the second order", claimed to be the first of its kind in Inorganic Chemistry, was observed by them during fractional crystallisation of the diastereoisomers, tris-biguanidinium cobalt(III) chloro-(+)-tartrate. Tris-biguanidinium rhodium (III) complexes have been resolved into their optical isomers⁵. In the case of the rhodium complex, no "asymmetric transformation of the second order" could be detected. The present work was undertaken to study the optical behaviour of tris-biguanidinium iridium(III) salts.

Tris-biguanidinium iridium(III) chloride was resolved by forming diastereoisomer, ($\pm$)-tris-biguanidinium iridium (III) chloro-(+)-tartrate, which was then fractionally crystallised. The least soluble fractions was *laevo*-rotatory like the rhodium analogue and as observed by Werner⁶ in the case of the resolution of other complexes of iridium.

From the less solubility of the *laevo*-rotatory tris-biguanidinium cobalt (III), rhodium (III), and iridium(III) chloro-(+)-tartrate, a correspondence in the configuration of the *laevo*-isomers is suggested.

1. Rây, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 313.
2. Sinha and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 179.
3. Ghosh and Sinha, *Science & Culture*, 1961, 27, 312.
4. Rây and Dutta, *this Journal*, 1941, 20, 289.
5. Ghosh and Sinha, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 249.
6. *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1228.

On continuing the fractionation, the rotation gradually diminished, finally reversing the sign; thus *dextro*-isomers were readily obtained. No asymmetric transformation like the corresponding cobalt complex was observed.

The active complex, chloro-(+)-tartrate, was converted into the relatively insoluble sulphates by metathesis with ammonium sulphate. The chloride and nitrate were obtained from these sulphates.

The average molecular rotation of tris-biguanidinium iridium(III) complexes is the least in the series of cobalt(III), rhodium(III), and iridium(III), which is in agreement with the Jaeger's observation⁷.

Tris-biguanidinium iridium(III) complexes are extremely stable optically. Solid active samples can be preserved without loss of activity for months. The active complexes are also quite inert in aqueous solution. Racemisation could not be effected even on boiling an aqueous solution of the (–)-complex chloride with activated charcoal. Like the rhodium analogue, this behaviour is in strong contrast to the easy racemisation of the active tris-biguanidinium cobalt(III) salts and may be attributed to the greater stability of metal-ligand bonding.

EXPERIMENTAL

(±)-*Tris-biguanidinium Iridium(III) Chloro-(+)-tartrate*.—A solution of tris-biguanidinium iridium chloride was treated with the molecular proportion of freshly prepared silver (+)-tartrate, dissolved in water. The precipitated AgCl was filtered and the filtrate on evaporation left a pale yellow residue. The compound is fairly soluble in water. {Found: Ir, 26.5; N, 30.2; Cl, 4.90; H₂O (by loss at 120°), 4.50. Calc. for [Ir (BigH⁺)₃]Cl·(+)-C₄H₄O₆·2H₂O: Ir, 26.87; N, 29.37; Cl, 4.96; H₂O, 5.03%}.

(–)-*Tris-biguanidinium Iridium(III) Chloro-(+)-tartrate*.—A sample of the above racemic complex, dissolved in a small volume of water, was allowed to evaporate slowly. The first crop of crystals was found to be *laevo*-rotatory, which was fractionally crystallised till the two least soluble portions showed the same rotation. The substance was quite stable optically as a solid sample kept for six months did not show any appreciable loss in rotation. The sample contained 26.5% iridium. Calc. for [Ir (BigH⁺)₃] Cl·(+)-C₄H₄O₆·2H₂O: Ir, 26.87%. For a 0.5% aqueous solution at 31°±2°: $\alpha_D - 1.25^\circ$; [α]_D – 125°; [*M*]_D – 893°.

(+)-*Tris-biguanidinium Iridium(III) Chloro-(+)-tartrate*.—After separation of a few fractions of the *laevo*-gyrate in the above fractionation, the subsequent fractionation showed very small rotation and finally became *dextro*-rotatory. Further fractionation was continued till two consecutive fractions showed the same rotation. {Found: Ir, 26.55. Calc. for [Ir (BigH⁺)₃] Cl·(+)-C₄H₄O₆·2H₂O: Ir, 26.87%}. For a 0.5% solution in water at 31±2°: $\alpha_D + 1.30^\circ$; [α]_D + 130°; [*M*]_D + 928°.

(–)-*Tris-biguanidinium Iridium(III) Chloride*.—A solution of the *laevo*-chloro-(+)-tartrate was allowed to react with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate when the (–)-tris-biguanidinium iridium(III) sulphate separated. This after recrystallisation from

⁷ *Chem. Abst.*, 1920, 14, 1087.

water was quantitatively decomposed with BaCl_2 , BaSO_4 removed, and the residue was evaporated to dryness. {Found: Ir, 32.2. Calc. for $[\text{Ir}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]\text{Cl}_3$: Ir, 31.95%}. For a 0.5% solution in water at $31^\circ \pm 2^\circ$: $\alpha_D - 1.2^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D - 120^\circ$; $[M]_D - 722^\circ$.

(+)-*Tris-biguanidinium*(III) *chloride* was similarly prepared from the *dextro*-chloro-(+)-tartrate. (Found: Ir, 32. Calc: Ir, 31.95%). For a 0.5% aqueous solution at $31^\circ \pm 2^\circ$: $\alpha_D + 1.1^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D + 110^\circ$; $[M]_D = +662^\circ$.

(-)-*Tris-biguanidinium iridium* (III) *nitrate* was obtained by metathesis of the *laevo*-sulphate with $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. {Found: Ir, 27.8. Calc. for $[\text{Ir}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{NO}_3)_3$: Ir, 28.2%}. For a 0.5% solution in water at $31^\circ \pm 2^\circ$: $\alpha_D - 1.0^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D - 100^\circ$; $[M]_D - 681^\circ$.

(+)-*Tris-biguanidinium iridium* (III) *nitrate* was prepared as above from the *dextro*-sulphate. {Found: Ir, 27.81. Calc. for $[\text{Ir}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{NO}_3)_3$: Ir, 28.2%}. For a 0.5% aqueous solution at $31^\circ \pm 2^\circ$: $\alpha_D + 1.02$; $[\alpha]_D 102^\circ$; $[M]_D + 694^\circ$.

The following anions and cations in the form of different salts were added to different solutions and kept under conditions indicated in Table I. In no case any detectable racemisation was observed. A 0.4% solution of *laevo*-tris-biguanidinium iridium (III) chloride or nitrate was used.

TABLE I

Substance.	Conc.	Time.	Temp.	Effect.
KCl	0.100M	24 hr	$31^\circ, 46^\circ, 52^\circ$	
$\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.010	"	"	No detectable
$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	0.011	"	"	change
Active charcoal ⁵	0.1g./20ml	12	46° and steam temp.	

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